

**Infrared Studies of Copper(II) Carboxylates :
Influence of Monosubstitution on Carboxy-
late Stretching Frequencies***

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THE infrared spectra of copper(II) carboxylates have been studied extensively. Nakamoto¹ and Catterick *et al*² have reviewed the situation upto 1978. Despite of enormous amount of data published only few references³⁻⁸ are available related with $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$, $\nu_s(\text{COO})$ and ΔE [the difference between $\nu_{as}(\text{COO}) - \nu_s(\text{COO})$]. Recently Srivastava has studied⁹ the influence of halosubstitution on molecular structure in copper(II) acetate. He has proposed the mode of coordination and eventually molecular structures on the basis of $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$, $\nu_s(\text{COO})$ and ΔE measurements. In the present investigation the influence of monosubstitution on the molecular structure has been studied with the help of $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_s(\text{COO})$ and using the ΔE as the main parameter.

Experimental

The complexes were synthesised by the standard methods reported in the literature^{7,10,11}. The purity of complexes were checked by comparing their ir spectra with the spectra available in the literature^{8,7,9}.

IR spectra were carried out at the Chemistry Department, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar, Punjab (India) in Nujol mulls over the range 4000-650 cm^{-1} at room temperature.

Results and Discussion

$\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_s(\text{COO})$ frequencies, ΔE and μ_{eff} values of the studied compounds and pK_a of the corresponding carboxylic acids are presented in Table.

If the $\nu(\text{COO})$ frequencies of the anhydrous copper(II) acetate, propionate, *n*-butyrate, phenylacetate and α -naphthylacetate are compared, then, it has been observed that these frequencies are not shifted much by the increase in chain length and size of the R group. This behaviour could be explained as the pK_a values of the parent carboxylic acids do not differ significantly. pK_a of the carboxylic acids can be presumed as a σ electron density on oxygens of carboxylate group and consequently the Cu-O bond strength⁹. Therefore,

TABLE— $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$, $\nu_s(\text{COO})$ FREQUENCIES, ΔE AND μ_{eff} OF COPPER(II) CARBOXYLATES AND pK_a OF THE CORRESPONDING CARBOXYLIC ACIDS

Complexes	$\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ cm^{-1}	$\nu_s(\text{COO})$ cm^{-1}	ΔE cm^{-1}	μ_{eff} B.M.	pK_a
Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂ · H ₂ O	1605	1418	187	1.41 ^b	4.75 ^e
Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂	1593	1414	179	1.39 ^a	4.75 ^e
Cu(C ₂ H ₅ COO) ₂	1588	1408	180	1.36 ^d	4.87 ^e
Cu(C ₃ H ₇ COO) ₂	1589	1410	179	1.37 ^d	4.81 ^e
Cu(C ₄ H ₉ COO) ₂	1585	1405	180	1.44 ^b	4.26 ^e
Cu(α -C ₁₀ H ₇ CH ₂ COO) ₂	1594	1412	182	1.44 ^b	4.22 ^e
Cu(OHCH ₂ COO) ₂	1570	1400	170	—	3.98
Cu(BrCH ₂ COO) ₂ · H ₂ O	1607	1401	206	1.48 ^a	2.92 ^a
Cu(ClCH ₂ COO) ₂ · 4H ₂ O	1620	1412	208	1.42 ^a	2.85 ^e
Cu(FCH ₂ COO) ₂ · 2H ₂ O	1650	1454	204	1.38 ^a	2.55 ^a
Cu(CNCH ₂ COO) ₂	1635	1424	211	1.49 ^f	2.45 ^e
Cu(NH ₂ CH ₂ COO) ₂ · H ₂ O	1610	1387	223	1.80 ^b	2.95 ^e

a, ref. 9 ; b, ref. 10 ; c, ref. 18 ; d, ref. 19 ; e, ref. 20 and f, ref. 21.

the Cu-O (carboxylate) bond strength can be presumed to be approximately same and thus could not cause any influence on $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_s(\text{COO})$. It is worth pointing out that a higher $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ frequency is expected, as the pK_a value of phenylacetic acid is lower with respect to other corresponding carboxylic acids. It is probably due to steric effects which reduce the $\nu(\text{COO})$ frequencies.

$\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ frequency of copper(II) acetate monohydrate is increased by 12 cm^{-1} than that of anhydrous acetate. This increase in frequency is caused due to the coordination of H₂O molecule to the Cu²⁺ ion, which donates one pair of electrons. This increase in electron density results a more covalent character in Cu-O bond and increases the $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ frequency. Similar increase of 12 cm^{-1} is also expected for $\nu_s(\text{COO})$ frequency but it has not been observed. This might be due to the mixing of $\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$ and $\nu_s(\text{COO})$ as observed in sodium acetates¹².

For the remaining compounds, it has been observed that both of the $\nu(\text{COO})$ frequencies are shifted in the same direction upon changing the carboxylate ligand except for copper(II) glycinate monohydrate. This suggests that symmetric nature of COO group in these complexes is still retained. In case of copper(II) glycinate monohydrate the $\nu_s(\text{COO})$ frequency lowers very much while $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ is practically unchanged with respect to that of copper(II) acetate monohydrate. An increase in $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ frequency is expected for a symmetric structure of COO group¹. It has not been observed probably due to the hydrogen bonding on COO group with either amino acid or H₂O molecule and overlapping of $\nu_{as}(\text{COO})$ with NH₂⁺ and NH₂ deformation frequencies.

X-ray studies of the metal acetates showed the $\text{CH}_3\text{C}(\text{O})\text{O}-\frac{1}{2}$ ion can coordinate to the metal atom

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in the following four possible ways¹ :

Possible ways of co-ordination of the acetate ion to the metal atom.

Some earlier workers^{9,10,14} have used the ΔE , as a parameter to predict the mode of coordination of the COO group to the central metal ion in various metal carboxylates. They suggested that ΔE should decrease in the following order :

It is obvious from the Table that the ΔE values of anhydrous copper(II) acetate, propionate *n*-butyrate, phenyl acetate and α -naphthyl acetate are in the same range as that for the copper(II) acetate monohydrate. Thus these complexes should have dimeric bridged cage type of structure similar to that of copper(II) acetate monohydrate which is well established on the basis of various studies¹⁵⁻¹⁷. The proposed structures are also supported by their magnetic moments, which are in the same range.

The ΔE value of copper(II) glycolate is 170 cm^{-1} , which is lower than that (187 cm^{-1}) of copper acetate monohydrate. Thus this compound should have structure either III or I of the COO group. It is rather more symmetrical than the glycolate ion of sodium salt¹⁸ as asymmetric COO stretching frequency (1570 cm^{-1}) of this compound is lower than that (1592 cm^{-1}) of the sodium salt. Thus the structure I for the carboxylate group and consequently monomeric symmetric structure for the compound has been proposed.

The ΔE value of copper(II) monohaloacetate, cyanoacetate and glycinate are slightly higher than that of copper(II) acetate monohydrate. This suggests either a structure II or structure IVb for COO group of these complexes. However, the structure II for COO group of the haloacetate and cyanoacetate cannot explain the subnormal magnetic moments varying within 1.38 to 1.49 B.M. for these complexes. Therefore, these compounds must have dimeric bridged cage type of structure. There is an increase (30 cm^{-1} or 42 cm^{-1}) in the asymmetric COO stretching frequency of the copper(II) cyanoacetate (1635 cm^{-1}), than that of the hydrated copper(II) acetate (1605 cm^{-1}) and anhydrous acetate (1593 cm^{-1}) respectively. The large increase in $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ could arise from the

effect of the cyanide substitution in acetate ligand. This suggests the coordination of the nitrogen atom of cyanoacetate group to the Cu^{2+} ion of the other dimeric bridged cage unit at trans-axial position. The above conclusion has also been strengthened by the higher ΔE value of copper(II) cyanoacetate to acetate complexes of copper(II). Wasson *et al*⁹, has also suggested such type of structure for the cyanoacetate of copper(II). Similarly on the basis of higher value of ΔE (223 cm^{-1}) of copper(II) glycinate monohydrate as compared to hydrated copper(II) acetate (187 cm^{-1}), a monodentate asymmetric nonresonating structure of COO group has been assumed, which is further supported by normal magnetic moment (1.80 B. M.) of copper(II) glycinate monohydrate.

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References

1. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley & Sons, 1978, p. 250.
2. J. CATHERICK and P. THORNTON in "Advances in Inorganic and Radio-Chemistry", (Eds) H. J. ENBLERUS and A. G. SHARPE, Academic Press, New York, 1977, Vol 20, p. 291.
3. Y. KURODA, *J. Chem. Soc. Japan, Pure Chem. Sect.*, 1961, 82, 1624.
4. A. V. R. WARRIER and P. S. NARAYANAN, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1967, 23A, 1031.
5. K. NAKAMOTO, Y. MORIMOTO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4528.
6. J. A. FANIRAN and K. S. PATEL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, 36, 2261.
7. J. R. WASSON, C. I. SHYR and C. TRAPP, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 1968.
8. P. V. BAKORE, *Curr. Sci.*, 1968, 37, 193.
9. C. P. SRIVASTAVA, D Sc. Discertation, State Univ. of Ghent, Belgium, 1975.
10. M. KONDO and M. KUHO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, 62, 1558.
11. J. PLOQUIN, *J. Bull. Soc. Chim.*, France, 1951, 18, 757.
12. A. S. TYAGI and C. P. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, (Communicated).
13. A. B. P. LEVER and D. OGDEN, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1967, 2041.
14. S. F. PAVKOVIC, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, 33, 1475.
15. G. M. BROWN and R. CHIDAMBARAM, *Acta Cryst.*, 1973, B 29, 2393.
16. M. KONDO and M. KUHO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, 62, 468.
17. A. M. HEYNS, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 1972, 11, 93.
18. R. C. WEAST, "Hand Book of Chemistry and Physics", 58th Ed. 1977-78, p. D-160, D-161.

19. M. KATO, H. B. JONASSEN and J. C. FANNING, *Chem. Revs.*, 1964, **64**, 99.
 20. J. LEWIS and R. C. THOMPSON, *Nature*, 1963, **200**, 468.
 21. W. E. HATIFIELD, H. M. MCGUIRE, J. S. PASCHAL and R. WHYMAN, *J. Chem. Soc. A.*, 1966, 1194.

LANAS as a Metallochromic Indicator in the Complexometric Estimation of Zinc, Cadmium and Mercury

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THE reddish brown azo-dye 2-(2'-lepidylazo)-1-naphthol-4-ammonium sulphonate, LANAS (I) formed by the condensation of 1,2-naphthoquinone-4-sodium sulphonate with 2-hydrazinolepidine in presence of concentrated ammonia, is found to give sensitive colour reactions with a number of metal ions¹.

The two five membered chelate rings are formed with metal ions, involving asterisk azo nitrogen, nitrogen of quinoline ring and hydroxyl of the naphthalene ring. The colour of chelates of zinc, cadmium and mercury are discharged quickly on adding EDTA solution, so that this dye can serve as indicator in EDTA titrations.

Experimental

Dye-solution : A 0.01% (w/v) solution of LANAS in double distilled water was used as indicator in EDTA titrations.

Reagents : Standard solutions (ca 10⁻³M) of zinc, cadmium and mercury were prepared by dissolving analytical grade zinc oxide, cadmium or mercury metal in perchloric acid. A 10⁻²M EDTA (disodium salt) solution was prepared and standardised against zinc solution with eriochrome black T as indicator. All chemicals were of analytical grade and twice distilled water was used throughout.

Recommended Procedure : To the metal solution containing 0.326 to 10.462 mg of zinc, 0.281 to 11.242 mg of cadmium and 1.0 to 200 mg of mercury, add 2 to 3 drops of 0.01% (w/v) LANAS solution and the requisite buffer (Table 1) to bring the required pH. Raise the volume to ~20 ml and titrate the contents under the given conditions with standard EDTA solution till the end point is reached.

Results and Discussion

The titrations can be performed in reverse order when dye (I) is used, cadmium(II) can be titrated between 40°-95°. All other titrations can be carried out at room temperature. In the titration of cadmium(II) addition of few drops of acetone just near the end point improves the visual change in colour at the end point. Some of the conditions necessary for the titrations are summarised in Table 1. The results of mercury(II) estimation have already been reported¹ and have been included for comparison.

In order to ensure the utility of the titration procedures, effect of various diverse ions has been studied in detail in the estimation of 1.307 mg of zinc, 2.248 mg of cadmium and 2.006 mg of mercury. The results of the studies are summarised below.

Zinc(II) estimation : The following ions did not cause interference upto the mg level mentioned in parentheses.

Fluoride, bromide, iodide(100), nitrite, nitrate, thiocyanate, sulphite, thiosulphate, tartrate, urea, ascorbic acid, borate, calcium(II) and barium(II) (80); oxalate, rhodium(III), ruthenium(III), iridium(III), platinum (II & IV), palladium(II) and copper(II)^{a,b} in equal amounts; chromate (28); phosphate (25); magnesium(II) (30); cadmium(II)^d and lanthanones(III)^e (1.5); mercury(II)^a (20); lead(II)^e (3); aluminium(III)^e (4); bismuth(III) (6) and tin(II)^e (2.8).

Cadmium(II) estimation : Fluoride, bromide (100); nitrate, nitrite, thiocyanate, sulphite, tartrate, thio-urea, hydroxylamine, borate and barium(II) (80); oxalate, calcium(II) (80); urea, phosphate (40); ascorbic acid, chromate (2); thiosulphate (12); platinum and platinum metals (1.0); copper(II)^a, lanthanides(III)^e (1.5); aluminium(III)^e (2.0); bismuth(III)^f (2.0); iron(III)^e and tin(II)^e (1.0).

In case of mercury(II) estimation the interferences are of the same order¹. Oxalate could be tolerated in large amounts. Iron, bismuth, lead and aluminium could be successfully masked. In this

a = masked with thiourea; b = with thiosulphate; c = fluoride;
 d = with iodide; e = with sulphate; f = with chloride.